

Digitalisation in Indian Rural Marketing: Awareness of Digital usage in Rural Marketing

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:.

Shanthala, M.,
and Geetha Shree.
“Digitalisation
in Indian Rural
Marketing: Awareness
of Digital Usage in
Rural Marketing.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Arts, Science
and Humanities*, vol.
6, no. S1, 2018, pp.
150–154.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.1404495](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1404495)

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Abstract

The virtual marketing in India is accelerating and rapidly growing in rural areas of the country. Their progress depends on the ability to figure out the basic factors which is needed in the rural area for the development of the society. This paper makes out the high importance of online infrastructure and the effectiveness of internet connectivity with one mission and target and even explains the purpose to take nation forward digitally and economically. This paper initiates and ensures that how people are getting engaged in the innovation process (AI) which is necessary for the sound growth in rural backward areas. It also brings out the significance of sustainable development of the country with the full potential usage of digitalization in rural marketing. And finally figure outs the challenges to be faced by govt. As well as corporate bodies in the way of successful implementation of digital illiteracy, poor infrastructure, lack of coordination among various departments and also issue pertaining in creating opportunities for the common public of the country (rural backward areas) and therefore to make a point (conclude) realizing the vital heights of the effective usage of artificial intelligence and combined effort of both public, govt. And corporate bodies, industrial sectors involvement and their continuous dedication in the field of rural marketing will definitely bring the effective progress in rural marketing.

Keywords: Rural, Digitalization, Economic, Backward Areas, Infrastructure & Sustainable Development.

Introduction

Digitalisation is now plays a vital role in the scope of Artificial intelligence & also it is known as the sound source for the development of India with which Indian economy can anticipate effective improvement in the growth of Rural Marketing by making optimal usage of digitalisation in rural areas .

The overall progress of the Rural Marketing completely depends on the ability of planning, execution, & finally how well we implement the artificial intelligence in the rural area and figure outs the factors which determines the need for the sound development of the society. The virtual marketing in India is accelerating and rapidly growing in

rural areas of the country. Now it is the right time for Indian companies to pursue digitalisation. Whereby it generates profitable revenue to the government of India.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to analyse the high importance of online infrastructure and the effectiveness of internet connectivity and also brings out the significance of sustainable development of the country with the full potential usage of digitalisation in rural marketing

Objectives of the Study

- To figure out the high importance of digitalisation in rural marketing.
- To examine whether digitalisation practices influences the significant growth in Indian economy.
- To find out the opportunities and challenges pertaining to digital rural India.
- To ascertain whether a combined effort or individual effort of government and corporate sector enhances the Digital rural marketing growth.

Literature Review

Implementation and Creating awareness pertaining to the usage of digitalisation. It is very much necessary to make a point about taking initiatives in implementation of digitalisation in and around rural areas in perspective of the rural marketing. The need for artificial intelligence today is grown to the level of nothing is impossible status. Digitalization in marketing leads to changes from traditional marketing to modern marketing.

Initiative taken by Intel (2015) in Hyderabad relating to bring awareness in digitalization by launching 'Ek Kadam Unnati Ki Aur', an initiative aimed at working with the government to create the blueprint for the digitization of rural India. Launched in June 2000, ITC'S E-CHOUPAL initiative has emerged as the largest internet based intervention in rural India. Google has launched in 2014 an initiative to introduce women to the internet especially those in the rural areas. They have launched a website 'helping women get online'.

Pooja and Neha (2014) in their study examined the scope of rural marketing in India. They concluded in their findings that there exists a large scope of marketing, provided that improvement in infrastructures is carried out. It also stated that the rural market is yet to be exploited.

Edward J. Malecki (2003) worked on the potential and pitfalls of digital development in rural areas. Clearly there are potential benefits of the digitalization in rural area which increases the efficiency of the work but it also has downfalls like it would be the cause of shortage of human capital. As there is increase in technology the goods and services are available at a click away from people and that has reduced the human interaction. Internet and mobile have become integral part of our life, whether in case of telecommunication, entertainment or marketing. The increase in the digital economy also.

Nowadays in rural areas also have social interactions through networking apps and it is increasing, mouth word is the form of feedback for any product usage. Common platform should be given to everyone where they can share their opinions and reviews. Young human minds interference makes huge differences in bringing creative thoughts and ideas to overcome the problems faced by the Indian economy relating to the key factors as below:

- Creation of employment opportunities in rural areas leads to decrease in poverty level.
- Decrease in poverty level will leads to the increase in individual cost of living
- Increase in cost of living will leads to the self satisfaction.

- If Self satisfaction is promised to each individuals then we can definitely turn our Indian economy towards sustainable development
- Finally if we anticipate sustainable development overall growth of the economy is possible.

Key Role of Digitalising Rural Indian Marketing

How digital marketing enhance the scope for rural marketing in rural India

With reference to the above cited main point it is important to the citizen of India to figure out the right platform to the right crowd, and also it is very much important to make sure to move forward with the right content. Most importantly putting an effort to understand the human minds (consumer journey) is foremost factor which will take our nation towards developing marketing rural India.

For instance:

KKT(KAN KAJURA TESAN) The radio channel that was accessed through missed calls, and it is the first fully advertiser funded mobile- based entertainment on- demand initiative in India. There focus is now to become the largest provider of content in rural India. Till date, KKT has secured four canne lions(three gold; one bronze), including a first ever gold for uniliver in the mobile space.

“IF YOU COULD BE JUST A ORDINARY NOTHING COSTS BUT TO BE AN EXTRAORDINARY YOUR CREATIVE MIND MATTERS”

Research Methodology

The method of research used to bring out the results to this paper is questionnaire method. With total ten(10) questions we approached the common public residing in nelagadaranahalli our target samples age criteria was around 18 to 40 years.(young generation) and the sample size that we used is only 20 in number. And data analysis can be shown in the below table

Analysis based on our paper objectives

Objective	Stongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	20	9	39	31
2	14	6	17	22
3	13	18	19	20
4	9	6	18	7

Data Collection and Analysis

The study used both primary & secondary data. The bulk of secondary data was obtained from Internet. The primary data was generated through the use of oral interviews & questionnaire designed especially for this study. According to my respondents for the objectives which we have mentioned the output for my first and second objective is total 20 rating points for strongly disagree, 9 rating points for disagree, 39 rating point for agree and 31 rating points for strongly agree. Finally with the help of this small research the perseverance of the common public of nelagadaranahalli is that they give high importance to digitalisation and they even aware of digitalisation and they are also ready to welcome the concept digital India all over the country.

The output for my second objective was total 14 rating points for strongly disagree, 06 points for disagree, 17 points for agree, and 22 points for strongly agree. Hence I can easily interpret that the citizen of nelagadaranahalli anticipate that the awareness of digitalisation is necessary, they even agree that there will be more difficulties in the implementation of digitalisation in rural marketing. And they also strong believe that digital marketing will bring them the better employment opportunities to the young crowd of nelagadaranahalli.

The output result for my third objective is the total rating points for strongly disagree is 13 points, 18 rating points, 19 rating points for agree, and 20 rating points for strongly agree. Therefore with help of this data we can easily make sure that the young crowd of nelagadaranahalli is anticipating the growth of Indian economy with the implementation of digital rural marketing. The output for my fourth objective is that 09 rating points for strongly disagree, 06 points for disagree, 18 rating points for agree, and 07 points for strongly disagree. With the help of above data analysis we can figure out the high importance of digital rural marketing and also we can make out that implementation of digital rural marketing will create employment opportunities and that will lead to the individual development and also overall development of India.

Findings

- Indian young minds are rigorously waiting for the implementation of digital India
- The view point of nelagadaranahalli crowd towards digital rural marketing is positive
- The anticipation of sustainable development is difficult in a democratic country like India.

- The combined effort of both government and corporate sectors will take India forward (growth)
- The young pupils have many plans pertaining to the digital rural marketing.
- This small research study helped us to make out both merits and de merits involved in digital rural marketing.

Suggestions

- Indian government must take some necessary action in pertaining to the implementation of digital rural marketing.
- Corporate sectors must come forward with the necessary funds for incorporating digital rural marketing in India.
- Both government and industrial units must take care of rules policies that they bring in each amendment, only then the citizen of India can anticipate sustainable development in our country.

Scope of the Study

This study will be limited to Nelagadaranahali semi- rural backward area Bangalore. But we should not deny the point that the topic of this study has huge challenges to be faced.

Limitations of study

This study had limitations which include the problem of diverse coverage of rural areas it is limited only to the 20 samples. There was also the problem of time & uncompromising attitudes of some respondents encountered during the study as some respondents refused to fill the questionnaire while some respondents were not available to answer our questions despite several visits.

Conclusion

As per the survey population have to increase in rural areas by increasing the marketing values which adopts digitalization and creates more job opportunities by this population will sustain and they can implement newer technologies in business. Finally to conclude with this study I would highly appreciate the efforts put in by our government in implementing the concept digital India and also I request government India to take immediate actions regarding encouraging the young pupils of India by encouraging them with their innovativeness and creative thoughts. Hence complete and optimal usage of young generation (man power) will lead to the heights of success in digital rural marketing.

Web Sourses

Primary source and Internet browser:

<https://www.google.co.in/>

search?q=digital+rural+india&aqs=chrome..69i57j69i60j0l4.6623j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8